

NECROTIZING FASCITIS OF THE GENITALIA: A RARE CASE REPORT OF FOURNIERS GANGRENE WITH PYOCELE.

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ABSTRACT:

Fournier's gangrene is a severe, rapidly advancing necrotizing fasciitis of the perineal, genital, or perianal regions and necessitates emergent surgical intervention in addition to aggressive antibiotic management. Herein is presented the clinical course of a 55-year-old chronic smoker who initially presented with vomiting, low-grade fever, and acute painful scrotal swelling. Initial assessment revealed diffuse scrotal wall cellulitis, for which conservative treatment was begun. Nonetheless, owing to patient refusal of early surgical intervention, the infection advanced, and Fournier's gangrene with secondary pyocele ensued. Readmission with exacerbation of clinical signs—such as recurring fever, enlarging scrotal swelling, blackish pigmentation of the skin, bilateral funiculitis, and hydrocele—underscored the progression of the disease. Radiologic studies supported involvement of both local and systemic elements such as pericholecystic fluid and marked bowel loop prominence. The patient ultimately required scrotal exploration, debridement, and subsequently, orchidectomy with scrotal skin approximation. A complete medical regimen using dual IV antibiotics, supportive measures, analgesia, mucolytics, sitz baths, and local wound management was provided. The patient recovered favourably with the late intervention and was discharged in stable condition. This article highlights the supreme significance of early diagnosis, timely surgical intervention, and vigorous supportive treatment in Fournier's gangrene, particularly in patients with underlying risk factors like chronic smoking and history of physical exertion. Inadequate timing of surgical debridement may result in serious morbidity and possible mortality and is a pointer to increased clinical suspicion and patient cooperation in high-risk situations.

Keywords:

Fournier's gangrene, necrotizing fasciitis, scrotal cellulitis, pyocele, debridement, orchidectomy, chronic smoking, surgical delay.

INTRODUCTION:

Fournier's gangrene (FG) is a rapidly progressive, acute, and life-threatening, infective necrotizing fasciitis affecting external genitalia, perineal or perianal regions, which mostly occurs in men, but may also develop in women and children. According to the advanced management mortality remains high and averages 20–30%. [1] This unusual and serious condition was originally described by Jean Alfred Fournier in 1883. [2] Scrotal pyoceles, which are purulent collections between the parietal and visceral tunica vaginalis encasing the testicle, are uncommon urological emergencies that are sparsely reported in the literature. Pyoceles in adults arise after epididymo-orchitis infection most commonly, yet may also arise as a consequence of intra-abdominal infection and trauma. Early detection and correct management of scrotal pyoceles are essential to prevent the dreaded complication of Fournier's gangrene. [3] It occurs in approximately 2.5–6.5 per 100,000 persons per year. Infrequently, epididymitis may result in formation of pyocele, which is one of the most severe urological emergencies requiring urgent operation to avoid serious complications like Fournier's gangrene, permanent infertility, sepsis, or in some instances death. [4] Various terms have been used to denote Fournier's gangrene in the past including "streptococcus gangrene," "necrotising fasciitis," "periurethral phlegmon," "phagedaena," and "synergistic necrotising cellulitis." It is seen in all ages and has been described in both sexes. But the male to female ratio is 10:1. Death has been described in various series to be from 16 to 40%. It can occur as a patch of gangrenous skin of the scrotum or the whole skin of the scrotum can peel off. At times scrotal sparing with sole involvement of the penis can be observed. Extensions can extend up to thighs, abdominal wall, chest wall, axilla. Involvement of the testis is uncommon due to variations in the blood supply. Among the imaging tests, X rays are helpful in showing the presence of gas within soft tissues; ultrasound is more helpful as it can show the presence of diffuse edema, thickness of the scrotal wall and possibly the penis, and the presence of gas in the scrotum. (5) The diagnostic methods employed in Fournier gangrene are radiography, ultrasound, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging. On radiographing the infected site, gas can be visualized in the depth of the soft tissues, which is a definite indication for surgery and ultrasound is employed, which also serves to check blood circulation and testicular condition. [6] There are two clinical scoring systems applied to assess severity of Fournier gangrene, namely Fournier Gangrene Severity Index (FGSI) and the Laboratory Risk Indicator for Necrotizing Fasciitis (LRINEC). [7] The treatment is complicated and ranges from surgical measures, in an attempt to drain secretions and eliminate necrotic tissue, to performing special dressings aiming to making the injury ready for skin reconstruction. [8] Management of FG involves management of sepsis, stabilization of medical parameters and emergency surgical debridement of necrotized tissue, hemodynamic optimization with emergency resuscitation with fluids, and broad-spectrum parental antibiotics. Even in the face of early and vigorous treatment, the condition is life threatening. As discussed earlier, involvement of the testes in FG is rare and implies an intraabdominal or retroperitoneal source. Although orchiectomy is not often needed, it can be indicated in cases of widespread tissue loss in the overlying scrotum, groin and perineum resulting in cumbersome dressing changes. [9] The atypical but life-threatening progression of initially uneventful scrotal wall cellulitis to Fournier's gangrene complicated by pyocele is reported in this case report, illustrating the result of delayed surgery and the importance of early diagnosis, immediate debridement, and multidisciplinary management of high-risk cases.

CASE PRESENTATION:

A 55-year-old man with a history of chronic smoking for 20 years came to the General Surgery Department on March 19 for complaints of 18 bouts of vomiting, low-grade fever without rigors or chills, and acute onset of scrotal swelling and pain for three days. On clinical examination, there was a diffuse, spiral-shaped swelling of the scrotum of 12×12 cm with stretched, shiny skin, blackish discoloration, redness, and loss of rugosity. The swelling was cystic, fluctuant, tender, and with intact testicular sensations and normal cord architecture. Initial vitals and systemic examination were stable, and abdominal ultrasonography revealed diffuse scrotal enlargement. The initial diagnosis of diffuse scrotal wall cellulitis was given, and conservative management was initiated. Symptomatic worsening was seen with increased pain, erosion of skin, tenderness of the left testes, and thickening of the spermatic cord. Surgical exploration was recommended but refused by the patient, who was discharged with close follow-up orders. The patient was readmitted on April 1 with return of symptoms, such as vomiting, fever, and increasingly severe scrotal swelling. Recurrent scrotal ultrasonography showed left epididymo-orchitis, bilateral funiculitis (L>R), bilateral moderate hydrocele, and diffuse edema of the scrotal

wall which is a suggestive of pyocele. (See figure 2.) Abdominal ultrasound and POD-2 imaging revealed scanty pelvic free fluid, large small bowel loops, mild edema of the gallbladder wall, and a thin ribbon of pericholecystic fluid along the anterior wall of the gallbladder. The abnormal lab investigations seen in patient can be given in **Table-1**. Clinical correlation with these radiographic findings and the presence of bilateral scrotal swelling with blackish discoloration established the diagnosis of Fournier's gangrene with pyocele. The patient was done with spinal anaesthesia scrotal exploration and debridement and subsequently with orchidectomy with scrotal skin approximation on POD-6 for unhealthy sloughing wound edges. He was treated with a thorough treatment regimen consisting of IV antibiotics: Inj. Sulbacef 1.5 g IV twice daily, Inj. Metrogyl 500 mg IV three times daily, and Tab. Duonem ER 300 mg twice daily; analgesics: Inj. Dolokind Aqua IV twice daily, Inj. Paracetamol 1 g IV prn; gastroprotective: Inj. Pantop 40 mg IV once daily; antiemetic: Inj. Vomikind IV prn; enzyme therapy: Tab. Chymoral Forte DS three times daily; multivitamins: Tab. Limcee once daily and Syp.Ascoril LS 5 ml thrice daily; local antiseptic management: sitz baths with 10% Betadine in warm water three times a day for 10–15 minutes and Debridase ointment for local use; scrotal support, BP/TPR monitoring thrice daily, and Tab. Alprax 0.25 mg at night. The patient had a good response to the treatment and was discharged in stable condition afterwards. A Timeline of the patient's treatment & recovery is given in **Figure 1**.

Table 1. Abnormal Lab Values seen in patient.

Parameter	Result values	Biological references
Complete Blood Picture		
Haemoglobin	12.1	12-14 gm/dl
T.W.B.C	13,700	4,000-11,000 /cmm
Platelet count	17,800	4,000-11,000 /cmm
Polymorphs	89	50-70 %
Lymphocytes	04	25-40 %
Eosinophils	00	01-04 %
M.C. V	83	86-98 FL
ESR	30	0-15 mm/hr
Post Prandial Blood Sugar	120	70-110 mg/dl
Fasting Blood Sugar	141	110-160 mg/dl
Serum Electrolytes		
Sodium	133	136-146 mmol/L
Chlorides	108	96-106 mmol/l
Calcium	7.7	8.5-102 mg/dl
Liver Function Test		
Albumin	2.7	2.5-5 gm/dl
Total Proteins	4.8	6.0-8.3 gm/dl
Creatinine	1.6	0.7-1.3 mg/dl

Figure 2. Ultrasound showing Scrotal Wall Thickening with Pyocele and Inflammatory Changes –

Indicative of Fournier's Gangrene.

CASE DISCUSSION:

Fournier's gangrene is an aggressively progressive necrotizing fasciitis of the perianal, genital, or perineal regions, typically requiring urgent surgical debridement and broad-spectrum antibiotics. It is necrotising fasciitis and cellulitis of subcutaneous fascia right up to or even including muscle. Treatment provided was under cover of broad-spectrum antibiotics patients were then admitted for urgent wound debridement. [10] The following is a delayed presentation and progression from scrotal diffuse cellulitis to Fournier's gangrene with pyocele. Initial conservative management was limited by the patient's unwillingness for surgery despite clinical worsening of infection manifested by signs of

increasing infection such as increased tenderness, thickening of cord structures, and blackish discoloration of scrotal skin. Cord was thickened and tender. Treatment provided was conservative with rest in bed, analgesics and antipyretics, scrotal support. [10] Readmission also demonstrated systemic disease with persistent fever, vomiting, and signs of localized sepsis such as severe scrotal wall edema, bilateral funiculitis, and hydrocele. Ultrasound sonography pictures subcutaneous gas or emphysema within soft tissues and can be employed to distinguish scrotal lesions. The occurrence of gas in the scrotum is regarded as a pathognomonic sign of Fournier's gangrene. It may also be employed to measure the edema, the thickness of infected soft tissue, the augmented subcutaneous fluid and the augmented vascular permeability. [11] The course showed the importance of early surgical exploration in such conditions. Progressive infection of soft tissue and skin can lead to necrosis and defects along the scrotal and perineal area, sepsis or even death. The infection, however, progressed to invade the inner testes and penis in this instance. As per the literature, it is the second documented case with bilateral orchiectomy and penis amputation caused by Fournier's gangrene. This illness can lead to organ loss like testes and penis even when there is adequate therapy. [12] Though late, the patient eventually underwent scrotal exploration and debridement, with orchidectomy to follow later and scrotal skin approximation secondary to slough and necrotic tissue. Early hospitalization has a critical contribution to survival that is with the socio-economic status of the patient. Since low socio-economic status has been said by certain authors to continue holding an essential role in late patient admittance. Therefore, increased hospital stay duration, increased counts of the debridement which contributes to morbidity and mortality. [13] This case is a reminder of the extreme significance of early diagnosis, surgical debridement, and aggressive treatment of Fournier's gangrene to prevent mortality and salvage genital anatomy, especially in risk factor patients such as smoking and heavy lifting.

CONCLUSION:

This case highlights the pivotal role of early diagnosis and early surgical intervention in the management of Fournier's gangrene—a life-threatening necrotizing soft tissue infection. The patient presented with scrotal wall cellulitis-like symptoms initially and was treated conservatively but progressed to Fournier's gangrene because of refusal of an early surgical exploration. This delay resulted in the formation of complications such as pyocele, widespread tissue necrosis, and finally led to scrotal debridement and orchidectomy. The case illustrates how delayed presentation, even with obvious signs of systemic infection and localized sepsis, can deteriorate clinical outcomes. Risk factors like chronic smoking and history of physical exertion (heavy lifting) definitely played a role in progression of disease. Effective recovery after late surgical intervention and liberal antimicrobial treatment underscores that though Fournier's gangrene is a surgical emergency, education of the patient and early compliance is critical in enhancing prognosis. This case acts as a reminder to have a high index of suspicion with such presentations and highlights the importance of timely, multidisciplinary management to avoid unnecessary morbidity and salvage genital structures in high-risk patients.

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